

A new species of the huntsman spider genus *Pseudopoda* Jäger (Araneae: Sparassidae) from the Eastern Himalayas, India

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Abstract

A new species of the genus *Pseudopoda* Jäger, 2000, *P. cheppe* sp. n. is described from the Indian Himalayas. Detailed description and illustrations are provided.

Keywords: Arunachal Pradesh, diagnosis, description, taxonomy.

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Introduction

The genus *Pseudopoda* was established by Jäger (2000) with *Pseudopoda prompta* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1885) as its type. It is the third largest genus of the family Sparassidae Bertkau, 1872 with 124 described species, of which, twelve species are known from India – *Pseudopoda abnormis* Jäger, 2001, *P. akashi* (Sethi & Tikader, 1988), *P. ashcharya* Jäger & Kulkarni, 2016, *P. fabularis* Jäger, 2008, *P. hingstoni* Jäger, 2001, *P. minor* Jäger, 2001, *P. perplexa* Jäger, 2001, *P. prompta* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1885), *P. shillongensis* (Sethi & Tikader, 1988), *P. sicca* Jäger, 2008 and *P. straminiosa* (Kundu, Biswas & Raychaudhuri, 1999) (World Spider Catalog, 2018). The present paper deals with the description of a new species, *P. cheppe* sp. n. from Arunachal Pradesh, belonging to the *Pseudopoda martensi*-species group (sensu Jäger, 2001).

Materials and Methods

Specimen was handpicked and preserved in 70% ethanol. Morphological examination and photography was performed with a Leica EZ4 HD stereomicroscope. All images were processed digitally with the aid of LAS core software (LAS EZ 3.0). Line drawings

were prepared with the GNU Image Manipulation Program (GIMP) (Montesanto, 2015). Leg measurements are given as: total length (femur, patella, tibia, metatarsus, tarsus). All measurements are in millimeters. Spine description is as follows: prolateral, dorsal, retrolateral and ventral. The types have been deposited in the National Zoological Collections, Zoological Survey of India (ZSI), Kolkata. Abbreviations: ALE = anterior lateral eyes; AME = anterior median eyes; CH = clypeus height; DS = dorsal shield of prosoma; E = embolus; FD = fertilization duct; Fe = femur; Mt = metatarsus; OS = Opisthosoma; Pa = patella; PLE = posterior lateral eye; PME = posterior median eye; Pp = palpus; RTA = retrolateral tibial apophysis; S = spermathecae; T = tegulum; Ti = tibia.

Taxonomy

Family Sparassidae Bertkau, 1872

Genus *Pseudopoda* Jäger, 2000

Pseudopoda cheppe Caleb sp. n.

(Figs. 1-12)

[urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:CC1AF75C-9111-484F-A711-2CB0CB774EBB](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1462247)

Figures 1–4: *Pseudopoda cheppe* sp. n. holotype male (ZSI-6586/18) 1. dorsal view; 2. chelicerae, maxillae and labium; 3. eyes, dorsal view; 4. abdomen, ventral view.

Figures 5–8: *Pseudopoda cheppe* sp. n. holotype male (ZSI-6586/18) 5. male left palp, ventral view; 6. same, retrolateral view; 7. embolus detail, ventral view; 8. same, slight posterior view. Scale bars: (5–6) 0.5 mm.

Figures 9–12: *Pseudopoda cheppe* sp. n. 9. male left palp, ventral view; 10. same, retrolateral view; 11. embolus detail, ventral view; 12. same, slight proximal view. Scale bars: (9–12) 0.5 mm.

Type material:

Holotype: 1♂ (ZSI-6586/18) INDIA: Cheppe (28.6097° N, 95.4966° E), alt. 1583 m, Arunachal Pradesh, 01 September 2016, leg. Boni Amin Laskar.

Etymology: The specific name refers to the type locality. Used as a noun in apposition.

Diagnosis: Species is closely related to *Pseudopoda megalopora* Jäger, 2001, but differs in the following characters: male larger (13.4 mm) in comparison to *P. megalopora* (4.8 mm); cymbium longer and narrower distally than in *P. megalopora*; embolus ending at 11 o'clock position (comparatively shorter and stouter, ending along medial axis of palp at 12 o'clock position in *P. megalopora* (cf. Figs. 7, 8, 11, 12 with fig. 36k in Jäger 2001); embolic disc wide and protrudes slightly beyond the tegular and cymbial retrolateral margin (remains well within the margin in *P. megalopora*); RTA single, curving uniformly in retrolateral view (branched in *P. megalopora*).

Description: Male (holotype) (ZSI-6586/18): Medium sized heteropodinae. Body length 13.4. Measurements: DS length 6.6, width 5.7, OS length 6.8, width 4.3. Eyes: AME 0.30, ALE 0.46, PME 0.38, PLE 0.44, AME–AME 0.22, AME–ALE 0.10, PME–PME 0.32, PME–PLE 0.63, AME–PME 0.46, ALE–PLE 0.46, CH AME 0.70, CH ALE 0.51. Leg formula: II-I-IV-III. Spination: Pp 1310, 1010, 3100; Fe: I 324, II 423, III 323, IV 223; Pa: I–IV 101; Ti: I–II 2126, III 2326, IV 2226; Mt: I–II 1014, III–IV 2024. Measurement of palps and legs: Pp 10.71 (3.72, 1.46, 1.67, –, 3.86); I 31.83 (9.09, 2.20, 10.00, 7.37, 3.17); II 32.09 (9.70, 2.23, 9.91, 7.72, 2.53); III 27.14 (7.84, 1.90, 8.26, 6.15, 2.63); IV 30.79 (9.25, 1.97, 8.95, 7.84, 2.78). Promargin of chelicerae with three teeth and retromargin with four teeth, cheliceral furrow with ca. 49 denticles. Palp as in diagnosis. Embolus arising from 10–11 o'clock position on tegulum, sickle shaped, embolus accompanied by embolic apophysis. Spermophor distinct, widening as it reaches the tip, opening dorsally. RTA single, arising proximally to medially (Figs. 5, 6, 9, 10).

Colouration in ethanol: DS light yellow, fovea and radial furrows distinctly marked with brown colour (Fig. 1), ventrally pale; eye region dark (Fig. 3). OS reddish-brown with triangular creamy patch in posterior half and lateral black patches; mid-ventral region pale yellow with interspersed brown patches; lateral regions brownish (Fig. 4). Legs yellowish with spine patches on femora; distal segments brownish.

Female: Unknown

Distribution: India (Arunachal Pradesh).

Relationship: *Pseudopoda cheppe* sp. n. belongs to the *Pseudopoda martensi*-group s. str. due to the presence of a sub-distal embolic process (Jäger, 2001). The species is closely related to *P. megalopora* with respect to the shape of the embolic tip and close geographic proximity of their type localities. However, the RTA is single without any branching in *P. cheppe* sp. n. resembling *P. martensi* Jäger, 2001.

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References

- Bertkau, P. 1872. Über die Respirationsorgane der Araneen. Archiv für Naturgeschichte 38: 208–233.
- Jäger, P. 2000. Two new Heteropodine genera from Southern Continental Asia (Araneae: Sparassidae). Acta Arachnologica 49(1): 61–71.

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- Jäger, P. 2001. Diversität der Riesenkrabbspinnen im Himalaya -- die Radiation zweier Gattungen in den Schneetropen (Araneae, Sparassidae, Heteropodinae). Courier Forschungsinstitut Senckenberg 232: 1–136.
- Jäger, P. 2008. Three new *Pseudopoda* species from northern India (Araneae, Sparassidae, Heteropodinae). Revue Suisse de Zoologie 115: 515–526.
- Jäger, P. & Kulkarni, S. 2016. An unexpected new species of the genus *Pseudopoda* (Araneae, Sparassidae, Heteropodinae) from the Western Ghats in India. ZooKeys 577: 55–62. [doi:10.3897/zookeys.577.7848](https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.577.7848)
- Kundu, M., Biswas, V. & Raychaudhuri, D. 1999. New huntsman spiders (Heteropodidae: Araneae) from Buxa Tiger Reserve, Jalpaiguri, West Bengal. Journal of the Bombay Natural History Society 96: 98–105.
- Montesanto, G. 2015. A fast GNU method to draw accurate scientific illustrations for taxonomy. In: Taiti S, Hornung E, Štrus J, Bouchon D (eds.) Trends in Terrestrial Isopod Biology. ZooKeys 515: 191–206. <https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.515.9459>
- Pickard-Cambridge, O. 1885. Araneida. In: Scientific results of the second Yarkand mission. Calcutta, 1–115 pp.
- Sethi, V.D. & Tikader, B.K. 1988. Studies on some giant crab spiders of the family Heteropodidae from India. Records of the Zoological Survey of India, Miscellaneous Publications, Occasional Paper 93: 1–94.
- World Spider Catalog, 2018. World Spider Catalog (version 19). Natural History Museum Bern, online at: <http://wsc.nmbe.ch> (accessed on 30 January 2018).